

A FRAMEWORK FOR IoT-BASED REMOTE HEALTH MONITORING SYSTEM

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Abstract

Many countries have witnessed a growth in elderly populations because of the developments in health care. This necessitates technological improvements in home-based care services that are used widely by elderly people. The Internet of Things (IoT) offers a convenient mechanism for avoiding the distance and time limitations associated with the health monitoring system. It has led to the rise of remote health monitoring system where patient data can be conveniently collected without physical presence. Undoubtedly, the new technology has enabled fast and early detection and management of health problems. However, it has led to increased concerns regarding security and privacy of data collected from patients which inform the main objective of this research. Notably, patient's health information is very sensitive and personal and there is need to ensure confidentiality and security of the data. Doing this is a challenge when the data is stored in easily accessible and poorly managed health systems. Thus, this research study provides a complete framework involving authentication, access control, and confidentiality of health information. Patient users could be authenticated using biometric means such as face recognition while that of institutions or health professionals could entail electronic card using PUF technology to access data storage facility. To control of access, institutions can use identity-based cryptography instead of certificates. Secure data access can be safeguarded through biometric-based keystroke

analysis which analyzes pattern or manner of typing and prohibits session after an abnormality is detected. Importantly, by safeguarding privacy and security in remote monitoring systems institutions preserve and adhere to important ethical principles and build the trust of the patients. This way, they promote openness and truthfulness in giving of personal information when confidentiality is guaranteed.

Keywords: Internet of things, data safety, Privacy, Secure Access, Authentication.

1 INTRODUCTION

Like many other sectors, health care has undergone tremendous improvement and developments over the years that has led to better health outcomes and reduced mortality rate. As a result, the next few years are likely to be characterized by a growth or increase in elderly population due to high life expectancy levels. Such changes and the limitations of the traditional healthcare systems come with an even greater need for health service innovations. These reasons explain the increased adoption and application of the Internet of Things in remote health monitoring system. Remote health monitoring system refers to a situation where patient health information is acquired using wearable physiologic technology that obtained real-time health details and sent it using communication technology [1].

However, the internet of things is associated with different problems and issues as presented

by Kakria et al. [2]. These concerns include unavailability of real data during testing, power issues, privacy and security of information obtained, appropriate medical requirements, user-friendliness of devices and clinical validation. Security and Privacy are, however, among the most significant issues and hence form the basis of this framework [3]. The subject of privacy and confidentiality associated with remote health monitoring systems can be subdivided and explored under three main dimensions of authentication, access control, and confidentiality while offering a distinct evaluation strategy.

2 PROPOSED WORK

Notably, the research will achieve the set goals of ensuring security and privacy of patient data by adhering to specific research questions and objectives. The three main research questions explored in the framework include the design components of the IoT-based remote system, how security and privacy can be maintained when using IoT systems and devices as well as how the security and privacy can be obtained. The new strategies to achieve security and privacy will be enabled by the research objectives that entail definition of the remote system, development of a new framework and use of a prototype IoT monitoring system for evaluation purposes.

The methodology section entails a focused discussion of the techniques that can be used to achieve security under each of the established dimension; authentication, access control and secure data access. Authentication refers to a case where users logging in to the system are authorized using the criteria established for patient users and another for health providers. Patient users could be authenticated using biometric means such as face recognition that is readily installed in most smart devices. Facial recognition is preferred since it is easy to use and there is no complex equipment required to

implement it. One just needs a camera that is available in almost all devices. Furthermore, implementing facial recognition is relatively cheap. At the level of institutions or health professionals, authentication could entail the use of electronic card that uses PUF technology. The reason for using this technology is because of the large number of professional authorized to access the data in a hospital from doctors, nutritionists and nurses. The PUF involves using a pseudo random number obtained from the electronic chip that come with the card. The second component of security, control of access, was done through identity-based cryptography instead of certificates. Here users need to use a unique identity assigned at the configuration stage. At the same time, the system is adapted to add new authorized persons after user agreement process and their identity number is randomly generated. Upon authorization, the users then generate a personal key using Private Key Generator (PKG) on the basis of their identity. The user and the administrator preserve this key. Secure data access will be safeguarded through biometric-based keystroke analysis that analyzes pattern or manner in which one types on the keyboard and the session is prohibited after an abnormality is detected. Any of the two types of keystroke analysis, static and structured, can be used to ensure secure access. Static keystroke analysis involves assessing one's keystroke behavior on preset phrases at particular points of the system. For example, it can be done when one types the password and user identity. Dynamic analysis involves periodic and continuous monitoring of the keystroke conduct of an individual. For instance, it can be analyzed when one logs in and as progress to when they continue to browse different pages in the system. Thus, privacy and security is ensured through the four main phases of user authentication, provider's authentication, regulation of access control and evaluation of the different phases.

As part of the background, the framework presents the three perceptions of the internet of things and how different authors have approached the subject including the weaknesses of their studies. Firstly, it explores the three main architecture components of the remote system as wearable wireless sensors connected to body area network, communication network component and the service level architecture [4]. Internet of Things has been integrated with the health system in three main perspectives: cloud perspectives, network-centric IoT and data-centric IoT [5]. Importantly, the data-centric type is the most popular and has been used in gathering information and devices were specifically designed to perform specific medical needs and include various devices that use biosensors.

Scholars such Abdullah et al [6], Fenghou et al. [7], Mora et al. [8] among others have proposed different remote monitoring systems that present important cases for assessing authentication and security issues of the IoT centric health system. Liu et al. [9] also discuss the application of the network based IoT in optical communication. Further, Bhattasali et al. [10] investigated the essence of semi-continuous authentication on the remote system and used the biometric-based facial recognition mechanism to ensure trust authentication. The studies are essential in understanding the concept of security and privacy in systems. However, most of the studies have their limitations which the framework sought to improve upon in its discussion of the security issues affecting the adoption of IoT in remote health monitoring system.

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